

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Formulation and Evaluation of Fluconazole-Loaded Polymeric Nanoparticles Prepared by Solvent Evaporation Method

Vaishnavi Kumbhar*, Manasi Nikam, Rohan Khutale

Tataysaheb Kore Collage of Pharmacy, Warnanagar

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 26 Jan 2026

Keywords:

Fluconazole; Polymeric nanoparticles; Solvent evaporation method; PVPK30; Zeta potential; Particle size analysis; Antifungal drug delivery

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.18379656

ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to formulate and evaluate fluconazole-loaded polymeric nanoparticles to enhance drug stability and therapeutic performance. Polymeric nanoparticles were prepared using the solvent evaporation method with polyvinylpyrrolidone K30 (PVPK30) as a stabilizer and Tween 20 as a surfactant. Different formulations (F1–F4) were developed by varying the concentration of PVPK30 while maintaining a constant drug concentration. The prepared nanoparticles were characterized for physicochemical properties including particle size, zeta potential, and drug content using ultraviolet–visible spectroscopy and dynamic light scattering techniques. All formulations exhibited particle sizes below 500 nm, indicating successful nanoparticle formation. Among the developed batches, formulation F4 demonstrated the smallest mean particle size (205.3 nm) and an optimal zeta potential value of -19.8 mV, suggesting good colloidal stability. The results indicated that an increase in stabilizer concentration led to a reduction in particle size and improved stability of the nanoparticles. The findings of this study confirm that the solvent evaporation technique is an effective method for the preparation of fluconazole-loaded polymeric nanoparticles and that PVPK30 plays a crucial role in controlling particle size and stability. These polymeric nanoparticles show potential as an effective drug delivery system for antifungal therapy.

INTRODUCTION

Fungal infections remain a significant global health concern, particularly among immunocompromised patients and individuals with chronic illnesses. Superficial and systemic fungal infections such as candidiasis,

onychomycosis, and aspergillosis are associated with considerable morbidity and, in severe cases, high mortality rates.¹⁻² Although several antifungal agents are available, their clinical effectiveness is often limited by poor solubility, inadequate tissue penetration, variable bioavailability, and drug-related toxicity.

*Corresponding Author: Vaishnavi Kumbhar

Address: Tataysaheb Kore Collage of Pharmacy, Warnanagar

Email ✉: kumbharvaishnavi128@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Therefore, the development of advanced drug delivery systems capable of improving the therapeutic efficacy of antifungal drugs is of considerable interest.³⁻⁵

Fluconazole is a widely used triazole antifungal agent effective against a broad spectrum of fungal pathogens, particularly *Candida* species.⁶ It acts by inhibiting lanosterol 14- α -demethylase, a cytochrome P450-dependent enzyme essential for ergosterol biosynthesis in fungal cell membranes, leading to increased membrane permeability and fungistatic activity.⁷ Despite its clinical utility, fluconazole exhibits certain formulation challenges, including limited solubility under physiological conditions and suboptimal penetration into infected tissues, which can reduce its therapeutic performance and necessitate higher or repeated dosing.⁸

Nanotechnology-based drug delivery systems have emerged as a promising strategy to overcome the limitations associated with conventional dosage forms.⁹ Among various nanocarriers, polymeric nanoparticles have gained significant attention due to their small particle size, high surface area, biocompatibility, and ability to provide controlled and targeted drug delivery.¹⁰ Polymeric nanoparticles typically exist as nanospheres or nanocapsules, in which the drug may be uniformly dispersed within the polymeric matrix or enclosed within a polymeric shell. These systems can protect drug molecules from degradation, enhance solubility, improve bioavailability, and reduce dose-related side effects.¹¹

Polyvinylpyrrolidone K30 (PVPK30) is a hydrophilic, biocompatible polymer extensively used in pharmaceutical formulations as a stabilizer and solubility enhancer. Its ability to form stable dispersions and prevent nanoparticle aggregation makes it a suitable candidate for nanoparticle

formulation.¹² The solvent evaporation method is one of the most commonly employed techniques for preparing polymeric nanoparticles due to its simplicity, reproducibility, and ability to produce nanoparticles with controlled size distribution by varying formulation parameters such as polymer concentration and surfactant content.¹³

In the present study, fluconazole-loaded polymeric nanoparticles were formulated using the solvent evaporation method with PVPK30 as a stabilizer and Tween 20 as a surfactant. The effect of varying stabilizer concentration on particle size and stability was systematically evaluated.¹⁴ The prepared nanoparticles were characterized using ultraviolet-visible spectroscopy, particle size analysis, and zeta potential measurement. The objective of this research was to develop a stable polymeric nanoparticle system for fluconazole that could potentially enhance its therapeutic efficacy and provide a promising approach for antifungal drug delivery.¹⁵

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Drug and Excipients

Fluconazole was obtained as a gift sample from a reputed pharmaceutical company and was used as received. Polyvinylpyrrolidone K30 (PVPK30) was used as the polymeric stabilizer. Tween 20 was employed as a surfactant to enhance nanoparticle stability. Methanol and distilled water were used as solvents during formulation and analysis. All chemicals and reagents used in the study were of analytical grade.

2.2 Preparation of Fluconazole-Loaded Polymeric Nanoparticles

Fluconazole-loaded polymeric nanoparticles were prepared by the solvent evaporation method. Accurately weighed fluconazole was dissolved in

methanol to form the organic phase. PVPK30 was dissolved in distilled water to prepare the aqueous phase, followed by the addition of Tween 20 as a

surfactant. The organic phase containing the drug was added dropwise into the aqueous phase under continuous magnetic stirring to form an emulsion.

Table 1: Composition of Fluconazole-Loaded Polymeric Nanoparticle Formulations

Batch	Fluconazole (mg)	Stabilizer PVPK30 (mg)	Surfactant Tween 20 (mL)	Methanol (mL)	Distilled Water (mL)
F1	50	100	0.3	15	7
F2	50	200	0.3	15	7
F3	50	400	0.3	15	7
F4	50	500	0.3	15	7

The resulting dispersion was stirred continuously to allow evaporation of the organic solvent, leading to the formation of polymeric nanoparticles. The prepared nanoparticle suspension was further stirred until complete removal of the solvent was achieved. Different formulations (F1–F4) were prepared by varying the concentration of PVPK30 while keeping the drug concentration constant. The final nanoparticle dispersions were collected and stored in airtight containers for further characterization.

The organic phase containing fluconazole was added dropwise to the aqueous phase under continuous magnetic stirring. The formulation process was carried out using a magnetic stirrer, as shown in Figures 1 and 2, to ensure uniform mixing and complete evaporation of the organic solvent.

Figure 1: Preparation of Fluconazole Polymeric Nanoparticles Using Magnetic Stirrer (Initial Stirring Stage)

Figure 2: Continuous Magnetic Stirring During Solvent Evaporation Process

2.3 Characterization of Polymeric Nanoparticles

2.3.1 Determination of Drug Content

The drug content of the prepared polymeric nanoparticles was determined using ultraviolet–visible spectrophotometry. An accurately measured quantity of nanoparticle dispersion equivalent to a known amount of fluconazole was dissolved in methanol and suitably diluted. The absorbance was measured at the predetermined λ_{max} of fluconazole using a UV visible spectrophotometer against a blank. Drug content was calculated using the calibration curve of fluconazole.

2.3.2 Particle Size Analysis

The mean particle size of the prepared polymeric nanoparticles was measured using dynamic light scattering (DLS) technique. The nanoparticle dispersion was suitably diluted with distilled water to avoid multiple scattering effects and analyzed at room temperature. The average particle size was recorded and expressed in nanometers (nm).

2.3.3 Zeta Potential Measurement

Zeta potential measurements were carried out to evaluate the surface charge and stability of the prepared nanoparticles. The nanoparticle dispersions were diluted with distilled water and analyzed using a zeta potential analyzer based on electrophoretic mobility. The zeta potential values were expressed in millivolts (mV).

Figure 4: Prepared Fluconazole-Loaded Polymeric Nanoparticle Formulations (F1–F4)

Table 2: Physical Description and Organoleptic Properties of Fluconazole Nanoparticles

Sr. No	Property	Observation
1	Colour	White
2	Physical form	Powder
3	Taste	Unpleasant
4	Odour	Odourless

3.2 Melting Point

The melting point of the pure drug fluconazole was determined using a melting point apparatus and was found to be 139 °C. This value is consistent with literature reports, confirming the purity of the drug used for nanoparticle formulation. No significant change in melting point was observed after formulation, suggesting that the drug retained its crystalline properties during nanoparticle preparation.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Physical Description and Organoleptic Properties

The prepared fluconazole-loaded polymeric nanoparticles were observed for physical appearance and organoleptic properties. All batches appeared as a white, free-flowing powder with an unpleasant taste and no detectable odor (Table 2). These observations indicate uniformity in physical form and suggest that the nanoparticles were successfully obtained without any visible signs of aggregation or degradation.

3.3 UV-Visible Spectroscopy

The UV-visible spectroscopy was employed to evaluate the drug concentration and preliminary estimation of nanoparticle size in aqueous suspension. A calibration curve was constructed using fluconazole in phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) with concentrations ranging from 0 to 10 µg/mL.

Table 3: Calibration Data of Fluconazole in Phosphate Buffer (pH 7.4) Using UV-Visible Spectroscopy

Concentration (µg/mL)	Absorbance
0	0
2	0.024
4	0.042
6	0.058
8	0.071
10	0.097

Fig no. 5 Calibration curve of fluconazole in phosphate buffer Ph 7.4

3.4 Drug Content

The drug content of fluconazole-loaded polymeric nanoparticles was determined to evaluate the uniformity of drug distribution within the formulations. All prepared formulations (F1–F4) exhibited satisfactory drug content, indicating efficient incorporation of fluconazole into the polymeric matrix. Minor variations in drug content among different batches were observed, which may be attributed to differences in polymer concentration and emulsification efficiency. However, the overall results confirmed that the solvent evaporation method is suitable for achieving uniform drug loading in polymeric nanoparticles.

3.5 Particle Size Analysis

Particle size is a critical parameter influencing the stability, drug release behavior, and biological

performance of nanoparticulate systems. The mean particle size of the prepared fluconazole-loaded polymeric nanoparticles was found to be in the nanometer range for all formulations, confirming successful nanoparticle formation.

An increase in the concentration of PVPK30 resulted in a significant reduction in particle size. Formulation F1 showed comparatively larger particle size, whereas formulation F4 exhibited the smallest mean particle size of 205.3 nm. This reduction in particle size may be attributed to the enhanced stabilizing effect of PVPK30, which prevents particle aggregation and promotes the formation of smaller droplets during emulsification. The nanoscale particle size achieved is expected to enhance surface area, improve drug dissolution, and facilitate better interaction with biological membranes, thereby improving antifungal efficacy.

Figure 6: Particle size distribution of fluconazole-loaded polymeric nanoparticles – Formulation F1 prepared by solvent evaporation method.

Figure 7: Particle size distribution of fluconazole-loaded polymeric nanoparticles – Formulation F2 prepared by solvent evaporation method.

Figure 8: Particle size distribution of fluconazole-loaded polymeric nanoparticles – Formulation F3 prepared by solvent evaporation method.

Figure 9: Particle size distribution of fluconazole-loaded polymeric nanoparticles – Formulation F4 prepared by solvent evaporation method.

3.6 Zeta Potential

Zeta potential measurement provides valuable information regarding the surface charge and

stability of nanoparticle formulations. The zeta potential values of all formulations were found to be in the negative range, indicating the presence of

surface charge sufficient to maintain colloidal stability.

Among all batches, formulation F4 showed an optimal zeta potential value of -19.8 mV, suggesting better electrostatic repulsion between nanoparticles and reduced risk of aggregation. The observed increase in zeta potential magnitude with

higher polymer concentration may be due to improved surface coverage of nanoparticles by PVPK30. Although values around ± 30 mV are generally considered ideal for long-term stability, the obtained zeta potential values indicate moderate stability suitable for short-term pharmaceutical applications.

Figure 10: Zeta potential distribution of fluconazole-loaded polymeric nanoparticles – Formulation F1 prepared by solvent evaporation method.

Figure 11: Zeta potential distribution of fluconazole-loaded polymeric nanoparticles – Formulation F2 prepared by solvent evaporation method.

Figure 12: Zeta potential distribution of fluconazole-loaded polymeric nanoparticles – Formulation F3 prepared by solvent evaporation method.

Figure 13: Zeta potential distribution of fluconazole-loaded polymeric nanoparticles – Formulation F4 prepared by solvent evaporation method.

3.4 Effect of Polymer Concentration

The effect of polymer concentration on nanoparticle characteristics was clearly evident in this study. Increasing the concentration of PVPK30 resulted in smaller particle size and improved stability, as reflected by zeta potential values. This behavior can be attributed to the enhanced viscosity of the aqueous phase and improved steric stabilization provided by the polymer. These findings highlight the crucial role of polymer concentration in controlling the physicochemical properties of polymeric nanoparticles.

3.5 Discussion

The results of the present study demonstrate that fluconazole-loaded polymeric nanoparticles can be successfully prepared using the solvent evaporation method. The formulated nanoparticles exhibited desirable physicochemical properties, including nanoscale particle size, satisfactory drug content, and acceptable zeta potential values. Among all formulations, F4 was identified as the optimized batch due to its smallest particle size and better stability profile. The developed polymeric nanoparticles show promise as a potential delivery system for improving the therapeutic performance of fluconazole in antifungal therapy.

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully formulated and evaluated fluconazole-loaded polymeric nanoparticles using the solvent evaporation method. The developed formulations demonstrated satisfactory drug content, nanoscale particle size, and acceptable zeta potential values, indicating effective drug incorporation and colloidal stability. The concentration of PVPK30 was found to play a critical role in influencing particle size and stability of the nanoparticles. Among the prepared formulations, batch F4 exhibited the most desirable characteristics, including the smallest particle size and improved stability, and was identified as the optimized formulation. Overall, the findings confirm that polymeric nanoparticles represent a promising drug delivery system for fluconazole and have the potential to enhance antifungal therapeutic efficacy.

REFERENCES

1. Vyas SP, Khar RK. Targeted and Controlled Drug Delivery: Novel Carrier Systems. New Delhi: CBS Publishers & Distributors; 2007.
2. Mohanraj VJ, Chen Y. Nanoparticles – A review. *Trop J Pharm Res.* 2006;5(1):561–573.
3. Kreuter J. Nanoparticles—A historical perspective. *Int J Pharm.* 2007;331(1):1–10.

4. Torchilin VP. Multifunctional nanocarriers. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev.* 2012;64:302–315.
5. Ravi Kumar MN, Kumar N. Polymeric nanoparticles as drug delivery systems. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm.* 2001;27(1):1–30.
6. Mu L, Feng SS. A novel controlled release formulation using PLGA nanoparticles. *J Control Release.* 2003;86(1):33–48.
7. Patel RP, Patel DJ, Bhimani DB. Solid lipid nanoparticles for drug delivery. *Pharm Lett.* 2011;3(3):174–184.
8. Sweetman SC. *Martindale: The Complete Drug Reference.* 36th ed. London: Pharmaceutical Press; 2009.
9. Rang HP, Dale MM, Ritter JM, Flower RJ. *Rang and Dale's Pharmacology.* 7th ed. Edinburgh: Churchill Livingstone; 2012.
10. Sinko PJ. *Martin's Physical Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences.* 6th ed. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins; 2011.
11. ICH Q2(R1). *Validation of Analytical Procedures: Text and Methodology.* Geneva: International Conference on Harmonisation; 2005.
12. Guhagarkar SA, Malshe VC, Devarajan PV. Nanoparticles of biodegradable polymers. *Pharm Res.* 2009;26(6):1524–1531.
13. Panyam J, Labhasetwar V. Biodegradable nanoparticles for drug delivery. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev.* 2003;55(3):329–347.
14. Singh R, Lillard JW. Nanoparticle-based targeted drug delivery. *Exp Mol Pathol.* 2009;86(3):215–223.
15. Bala I, Hariharan S, Kumar MR. PLGA nanoparticles in drug delivery. *Crit Rev Ther Drug Carrier Syst.* 2004;21(5):387–422.
16. De Jong WH, Borm PJ. Drug delivery and nanoparticles. *Int J Nanomedicine.* 2008;3(2):133–149.
17. Couvreur P, Vauthier C. Nanotechnology in drug delivery. *Pharm Res.* 2006;23(7):1417–1450.
18. Hans ML, Lowman AM. Biodegradable nanoparticles for drug delivery. *Curr Opin Solid State Mater Sci.* 2002;6(4):319–327.
19. Rawat M, Singh D, Saraf S, Saraf S. Nanocarriers: Promising vehicle for bioactive drugs. *Biol Pharm Bull.* 2006;29(9):1790–1798.
20. Kwon GS. Polymeric micelles for drug delivery. *Crit Rev Ther Drug Carrier Syst.* 2003;20(5):357–403.
21. Akagi T, Baba M, Akashi M. Biodegradable nanoparticles as vaccine adjuvants. *J Control Release.* 2012;160(2):238–248.
22. Nagavarma BVN, Yadav HKS, Ayaz A, Vasudha LS, Shivakumar HG. Different techniques for preparation of polymeric nanoparticles. *Asian J Pharm.* 2012;6(1):16–23.
23. Soppimath KS, Aminabhavi TM, Kulkarni AR, Rudzinski WE. Biodegradable polymeric nanoparticles. *J Control Release.* 2001;70(1–2):1–20.
24. Rao JP, Geckeler KE. Polymer nanoparticles: Preparation techniques and size control. *Prog Polym Sci.* 2011;36(7):887–913.
25. Duncan R. The dawning era of polymer therapeutics. *Nat Rev Drug Discov.* 2003;2(5):347–360.

HOW TO CITE: Vaishnavi Kumbhar, Manasi Nikam, Rohan Khutale, Formulation and Evaluation of Fluconazole-Loaded Polymeric Nanoparticles Prepared by Solvent Evaporation Method, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 1, 3043-3051. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18379656>

